

Building inclusive research organisations

How to use a data-driven approach to designing, implementing & sustaining Gender Equality Plans

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MINDtheGEPs
gender equality in research

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Disclaimer: The views and opinions expressed in this report are the sole responsibility of the author and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission.

Abstract

The *MINDtheGEPs White Book* provides a comprehensive, evidence-based framework for designing, implementing, and sustaining Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) in research-performing organizations (RPOs) across Europe. Developed within the Horizon 2020 MINDtheGEPs project, the document draws on lessons learned from seven partner institutions in five countries with traditional gender regimes—Italy, Poland, Ireland, Spain, and Serbia—spanning universities, public research bodies, and private sector R&D centers.

The White Book promotes systemic institutional transformation by addressing gender inequality at three interconnected levels: the individual (micro), organizational (meso), and cultural/policy (macro). Central to its approach is the shift from “fixing the women” to “fixing the system,” recognizing that lasting change requires restructuring institutional norms, governance, and practices rather than adapting women to pre-existing models of academic excellence and productivity. The document embraces feminist theoretical frameworks and intersectionality to analyze how structural barriers—such as the ideal of the “unconditional worker”—continue to marginalize not only women, but also other underrepresented groups in research environments.

Through extensive qualitative and quantitative data collection, participatory workshops, interviews, and comparative policy analysis, the project developed a stepwise approach to GEP implementation. Key pillars include: data-driven assessment and monitoring, participatory governance structures, dedicated training and capacity-building initiatives, strategic communication, and evaluation mechanisms designed to ensure long-term impact. The White Book also outlines methods for aligning GEPs with EU policy requirements, particularly the five mandatory thematic areas: work-life balance and organizational culture; gender balance in leadership and decision-making; gender equality in recruitment and career progression; integration of the gender dimension in research and teaching; and prevention of gender-based violence and sexual harassment.

As a practical guide, the White Book offers actionable recommendations, tools, and checklists aimed at practitioners, policy makers, and institutional leaders committed to building more inclusive, equitable, and effective research and academic institutions. By leveraging data, stakeholder engagement, and context-sensitive strategies, *MINDtheGEPs* provides a model for embedding gender equality as a core value and operational principle across Europe’s research and innovation landscape.

The design and the concept of this document have been a collaborative effort of the MINDtheGEPs research consortium that meet in a dedicated workshop in Rome on 23th and 24 January 2025.

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1. Introduction and aims of this white book

These practical guidelines follow and consider the changes introduced by the Horizon Europe Guidance on Gender Equality Plans (2021) delivered by the DG Research and Innovation of the European Commission. The contents proposed are aligned with those recommended by EIGE. The definition of practical guidelines for designing and implementing GEPs is based on evidence from data gathered during the different stages of the project, along with gained experience from sister projects.

The information in this white book is based on five different sources:

1. Indications from tasks carried out within the framework of the MINDtheGEPs project itself, including state-of-the-art review, narratives from interviews with partners, or other data collections.
2. Inputs from other projects oriented towards gender equality (such as GE Academy, GEAGendering academia, R&I PEERS, CALIPER, FESTA, GENERA, PLOTINA, TRIGGER, LIBRA, etc.)
3. Experience and existing actions from consortium partners. The MINDtheGEPs consortium consists of 10 different partners, each of them with a different form of organisation and with different initiatives implemented that can serve as feedback within the consortium itself to obtain ideas of good practices.
4. Additional materials provided by desk research, not only related to EU Gender Equality projects, but also any organisation that has been able to add value in some way in aspects related to gender equality.
5. Lessons learned through MINDtheGEPs workshops and activities.

The combination of all these tools served as indications to follow in order to develop the core of this deliverable. The proposed indicators have been sorted out by considering the best practices in existing GEPs.

Table 1. Micro, meso & macro level: what does it mean?

In the literature, gender imbalance is interpreted using mechanisms operating on three interconnected levels: the individual (micro), organizational (meso), and cultural (macro).

The individual – **micro level** – is focused on gender-characterized self-selection processes, for example competitiveness, scientific productivity, the balance between research and teaching, the field you chose to study, your parenting choices, and self-confidence. These mechanisms originate from socio-educational models, and the structural and organizational conditions within the academic space, where the problem of balancing work and caregiving burdens is exacerbated by the precariousness of early stage academic careers, that have critical implications for parenting choices and access to maternity and parental leave.

The organisational – **meso level** – is linked to organizational cultures (that are not gender neutral. Instead, most organisations operate with a masculinized model of worker, specific recruitment and promotion procedures (that fit men better), gender stereotypes that are reproduced in recruitment through review committee members, and the composition of committees that mirror late stage (predominantly male) higher positions in academic careers

The cultural – **macro level** – refers to the construction of criteria such as “merit” and “excellence”. When women do more teaching, they have less merit and with less time for research, there will be fewer publications, citations and other metrics that are considered key for assessing excellence .

2. Presentation of the MINDtheGEPs project

Over the past decades, the EU Commission has called for overcoming gender differences in research and innovation to stop the leaking pipeline and break the glass ceiling and the glass door. Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) have become firmly established as an eligibility criterion for receiving Horizon Europe funding. MINDtheGEPs is one of several H2020 projects aiming to support the development and implementation of GEPs in research-performing organisations. What makes this effort unique is the use of a data-driven approach to tailor measures to the needs of seven organisations under the project umbrella.

MINDtheGEPs have identified a multitude of obstacles that need to be addressed on the journey toward gender equality in research and innovation organizations. In line with the European Research Area's key priorities on gender equality, MINDtheGEPs aimed to remove barriers to recruitment, retention and career progression for female researchers, and improve work-life balance, addressing gender imbalances in decision making and strengthening the gender dimension in research and teaching. These barriers represent key challenges that need to be addressed in order to halt the waste of talent that is undermining Europe's future progress, and diversify views and methodologies to help increase the quality, methodological accuracy, and relevance of both research and the wellbeing of individuals and society. Moreover, the results from MINDtheGEPs shed light on how the dominant logic of science creates an ideal 'devoted unconditional worker' that is harmful for women, men, and the entire organization.

MINDtheGEPs takes a multidisciplinary, multidimensional approach to challenging gender imbalances across five different countries considered to have 'traditional gender regimes' in various types of Research Performing Organisations (RPOs). The partners designing and implementing GEPs represent five public universities (Turin, Tralee, Gdansk, Jagiellonian), one public research institute (National Research Council of Italy, CNR); one academic (University of Belgrade's School of Electrical Engineering, ETF) and one private company in the automotive industry (CTAG). The consortium is led by the University of Turin's interdisciplinary Research Centre for Women's and Gender Studies CIRSDe, representing an important knowledge base. The efforts are supported by three organizations bringing complementary expertise in monitoring and evaluation (Knowledge and Innovation), research communication (Uppsala University) and scientific publishing (Elsevier).

In order to promote systemic institutional change and following the "no data-no policy" principle, the project started by collecting and mapping data from the seven implementing organisations, and produced new qualitative and quantitative evidence with the help of tools from other projects run by CIRSDe. This data formed the basis for the design and implementation of actions that addressed both the structural and cultural levels of the seven organisations.

To address gender inequalities on the cultural level, MINDtheGEPs organised training, starting with joint 'train the trainers' workshops for all seven organisations, followed by training 'laboratories' tailored to different partners' needs.

To address inequalities on the structural level, MINDtheGEPs introduced measures designed to address work-family balance, making sure efforts that also target men were included, along with equality targets for decision-making bodies and for gender-sensitive research. The establishment of gender databases and governance structures for the project and the GEP created conditions that ensure the sustainability of actions beyond the project's life span. In all seven organizations, multidisciplinary teams (including key roles in middle or top management) were established, coupled with project

Advisory Boards (that include relevant national authorities), and professional associations both in STEMM and SSH, contributing to a successful change in RPOs and in society at large.

Efforts targeting both structural and cultural inequalities were designed to address the key areas identified by the European Commission: work-life balance and organizational culture, gender balance in leadership and decision-making, gender equality in recruitment and career progression, integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content, and measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment.

3. Seven locally grounded gender equality plans

3.1 National context: Italy

Italy ranks 12th in the EU on the Gender Equality Index with a score of 64.8, 3.9 points below the EU average. Since 2010, Italy's score has increased by 11.3 points, indicating a faster pace of progress compared to other EU countries. However, gender inequalities remain significant, particularly in the domains of power, knowledge and the workplace (European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE), Gender Equality Index, 2023).

Legislation addressing gender equality has evolved slowly, with gender quotas in politics established only in 2017. The 1991 Positive Actions law laid the groundwork, but effective implementation of Positive Action Plans (PAPs) only began in 2006. The National Code of Equal Opportunities between Women and Men (Dec. n. 198/2006) and decree number 5/2010 (implements Directive 2006/54/CE on equal opportunities and treatment for men and women in employment) mandate public organizations, including state universities, to create PAPs every three years, detailing actions to promote gender equality and allocate resources accordingly. However, the lack of specific guidelines allows organizations to independently determine their actions.

The Department for Equal Opportunities, founded in 1997, oversees gender equality but lacks sufficient resources. The Guarantee Committee for Equal Opportunities, established by Law n.183/2010, is responsible for implementing PAPs in research public organizations. While this law outlines a framework for the committee, it allows public administrations to define their own internal procedures and mandates the appointment of a Confidential Advisor to address harassment issues.

The only directive that contains indication for the development of PAP is the Directive of the Presidency of the Council of Ministers of 23 May 2007 on equal opportunities in public administrations, that identifies the instruments and the areas of intervention: positive actions aiming at balancing female representation in sectors and professional levels where they are underrepresented; the organization of work aiming at promoting work-life balance; hiring and promotional mechanisms targeting women.

University of Turin (UNITO)

Motto: Gendering science from culture to structure!

The University of Turin published its first Gender Equality Plan in 2023, as part of a Horizon 2020 project, MINDtheGEPs. As the first part of UNITO GEP, entitled "The Context," clearly establishes, in accordance with the basic principle of "No data no policy," the work on the GEP was preceded by a long phase of data collection and analysis. Developing a GEP that might effectively intercept the needs

of the academic community could not be achieved without conceiving a democratic, thoughtful, and participatory process. A horizontal process promoted by the UniTO research group responsible for MINDtheGEPs, which strongly favoured the involvement of all departments and administrative divisions. In fact, the UniTO GEP was discussed and designed with the Gender Equality Plan Implementing Board (GEPIB) and the Network of Delegates from departments and administrative directorates (set up by the MINDtheGEPs Project), through highly participatory meetings. It has been the subject of continuous exchanges with the CUG, the Rector, the Inclusion, Equal Opportunity and Gender Policy Delegate, and the General Director, and has ultimately been the subject of formal discussion in the Academic Senate before its approval.

The driving force behind the whole process of elaborating the GEP centres around the concept of gender justice, considered in an intersectional perspective. As many different barriers need to be overcome, a whole range of approaches has been adopted, comprising a virtuous mix of actions, to overcome the glass ceilings and glass doors. These actions must necessarily be both cultural and structural. We have, therefore, envisaged structural measures, such as a babysitting bonus and extra research funds or reduced teaching for those returning from maternity leave; the purpose is to provide support for women at a delicate time in their lives and careers, while also considering cultural actions that might revise our understanding of care as a feminine occupation and consider it instead as a right and duty for everyone, men included.

To see the UNiTO GEPs actions in details: <https://www.unito.it/ateneo/organizzazione/organi-di-ateneo/comitato-unico-di-garanzia/bilancio-di-genere-e-gep/gender>

National Research Council of Italy (CNR)

Motto: DATA-PLACED. The strategic role of data in addressing gender inequalities

In Spring 2022, the National Research Council of Italy (CNR) launched its first Gender Equality Plan (GEP) to promote equal participation in scientific and administrative activities. This plan focuses on enhancing diversity, combating gender discrimination, and ensuring transparency.

The GEP's development included analyzing administrative data, conducting interviews, and surveying staff perceptions. It consists of two main transversal pillars: A) Governance and monitoring for implementation and assessment, and B) Training and communication on gender equality issues along with five key areas.

A key achievement has been creating a data warehouse based on administrative data for intersectional analysis and implementing an annual Gender Balance Report since 2022. Following the "Train the Trainer" approach, CNR established a network of eight employees from diverse backgrounds and profiles who received specialized gender training. These employees became trainers for the CNR scientific network, which comprises more than 90 research institutes across Italy.

In 2023, a Gender Equality Team (GET) was established at the Presidency level to oversee GEP initiatives, promote equality, combat discrimination, and facilitate communication on gender policies. The GET includes diverse expertise focusing on governance, data monitoring, communication, training, and work-life balance, aiming to transform CNR's internal culture through collaboration and engagement

The CNR GEP is available here: https://www.cnr.it/sites/default/files/public/media/attivita/gender-equality/GEP_CNR_FINALE.pdf

3.2 National context: Poland

With 63.4 points out of 100, Poland ranks 18th in the EU on the Gender Equality Index in 2024. Its score is 7.4 points below the score for the EU as a whole. Since 2010, Poland's score has increased by 7.9 points, as much as the European average. Gender inequalities remain significant, particularly in the domains of power, and, to a lesser degree, knowledge, and work (European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE), Gender Equality Index, 2024). In SheFigures (2024) scores 72,4 points.

The principle of gender equality is embedded in the Polish Constitution and the Labour Code. Article 33 of the Constitution of the Republic of Poland (1997) states that men and women shall have equal rights in family, political, social and economic life, in particular regarding education, employment and promotion, and shall have the right to equal compensation for work of similar value, to social security, to hold offices, and to receive public honours and decorations. The Labour Code (1974) includes provisions on equal treatment in employment prohibiting discrimination on the grounds of sex, age, disability, race and other premises about establishing and terminating an employment relationship, employment conditions, promotion conditions, and access to training to improve professional qualifications and remuneration. The Labour Code also distinguishes between direct and indirect discrimination and identifies sexual harassment as a form of discrimination on the grounds of sex.

There is neither a separate legal act nor a set of provisions within a wider legal act referring to gender equality in research and higher education. The Act on the implementation of some regulations of the European Union regarding equal treatment (2010) sets general framework conditions for equal treatment policy in Poland and specifies the competent bodies in equal treatment issues, i.e. the Plenipotentiary for Equal Treatment as the government body and the Commissioner for Human Rights as the independent equality body. However, the Act does not cover discrimination based on gender in higher education. There is no reference to gender equality or equal treatment in the current Law on Higher Education and Science (2018), as there were no regulations concerning gender equality in the previous legal acts on higher education.

Although there is no official law on gender equality in research and higher education, organisations set up their internal regulations concerning the prevention of gender (and other forms of) discrimination and the promotion of gender equality. They do it as a response to requirements set by the European Union in its funding programs (including the GEP eligibility criterion in Horizon Europe), as a result of adopting the European Charter and the Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers and as an effect of participation in the EU-funded projects on structural change in academia.

At the same time, Poland has no legal provisions to enforce gender mainstreaming and thus there are no actions coordinated at the national level (EIGE, 2020). In 2025 the position of Plenipotentiary of the Minister of Science and Higher Education for Equal Treatment in the Area of Higher Education and Science has been established.

The University of Gdansk

Motto: Step by step - building an inclusive workplace for everyone

The first Gender Equality Plan for the University of Gdansk: Equality Measures for the years 2022 - 2023 (GEP for UG) was designed and introduced in 2021. GEP for UG has been elaborated by a dedicated group of experts from various fields, representatives of UG researchers and administrative staff and the core team members of the Horizon 2020 project MINDtheGEPs Modifying Institutions by Developing Gender Equality Plans (2021 – 2025). GEP for UG has been approved officially by the university authorities, the UG Rector in the order no 182/R/21 of 29 December 2021 and came into

action from January 2022. GEP for UG foresees a continuous institutional policy in this area and a periodic update of the planned measures

The design of the GEP for UG has been processed in compliance with the European Union's Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025 and according to the Horizon Europe Guidance on Gender Equality Plans. The development of the document was based on the diagnosis of the current institutional situation on equal treatment of women and men at UG based on qualitative and quantitative data gathered in materials and reports carried out at our university. Based on the data collected, GEP for UG was designed comprising 5 goals and 29 corresponding measures necessary to ensure a balance in achieving gender equality at UG. The goals set out in the GEP for UG refer to all 5 thematic areas recommended by the EU in the Horizon Europe Eligibility Criterion. Specific focus in the design has been put on training and awareness raising and dedicated training measures have been included in each of the 5 goals (GEP for UG measures 1.1, 2.1, 2.2, 3.1, 4.1, 5.1).

The first Gender Equality Plan for UG is the result of extensive collaboration between the university's managerial and executive staff, the university's organisational units, representatives of administrative staff of all levels, academics and researchers at all career stages representing both STEM (science, technology, engineering, mathematics) and SSH (social science and humanities) disciplines, university authorities and student representatives. Coordinating such cooperation and inviting so many participants was all the more challenging as the University of Gdansk is the largest university in the Pomorskie region, with 11 faculties, 2 international research centres, 4 doctoral schools, nearly 22,000 students and almost 1,800 researchers and 1,500 administrative staff. We are convinced that the overall positive result of GEP implementation is a great success for the entire community of the University of Gdańsk and The Fahrenheit Union of Universities in Gdansk.

The University of Gdańsk [Gender Equality Plan](#) is available to read in both English and Polish ([Plan wdrażania polityki równości płci](#)).

Jagiellonian University

Motto: Building a Future of Gender Equality Together"

The first Gender Equality Plan for the Jagiellonian University was adopted by Ordinance No. 94 by the Jagiellonian University Rector of 30 June 2022, to identify specific solutions for ensuring gender equality in the academic community. The GEP design was preceded by the analysis of the challenges facing the Jagiellonian University in terms of gender equality based on sex-disaggregated administrative data and the report prepared in 2021 by the Department of Safety, Security and Equal Treatment ("Gender at the oldest university in Poland" in Polish: [Bezpieczni UJ Raport Płeć na najstarszym uniwersytecie w Polsce](#)). The diagnosis of the status quo covered both different categories of employees and the students (including doctoral students).

An important part of the implementation of the GEP at JU are five working groups, engaging members of the university community and working on specific measures. These include a working group on the antidiscrimination procedure, on employee' satisfaction, on work-life balance, on gender in research and teaching and on inclusive language. Working groups meet on a monthly or bi-monthly basis. Participation is open to everyone from the university community and at every stage of GEP implementation. Meetings are organized, mostly, in a hybrid format to allow participants with different organizational and private commitments to join. In 2023, a position of the Gender Equality Officer was established, in 2025, the Gender Database Manager.

The GEP for JU is available here: https://rowni.uj.edu.pl/en_GB/gep-dla-uj

3.3 National context: Ireland

Ireland ranks 9th in the EU on the Gender Equality Index with a score of 73.4, which is 2.4 points above the EU average. Since 2010, Ireland's score has increased by 8.0 points, showing steady and notable progress towards gender equality. Despite this positive trend, gender inequalities persist, especially in the domains of power and time, with women underrepresented in decision-making positions and facing challenges in work-life balance (European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE), Gender Equality Index, 2023).

The principle of gender equality is firmly embedded in Irish legislation. The Irish Constitution (Bunreacht na hÉireann), while not containing a general equality clause, guarantees equality in specific rights such as education and family life. More comprehensively, gender equality provisions are detailed in statutory law, most notably the Employment Equality Acts (1998–2015) and the Equal Status Acts (2000–2018). The Employment Equality Acts prohibit direct and indirect discrimination on nine grounds, including gender, in employment, vocational training, and working conditions. The Acts also address sexual harassment and victimisation. The Equal Status Acts extend protection against discrimination to the provision of goods, services, education, and accommodation.

Ireland's commitment to gender equality in research and higher education is supported by a combination of national and sectoral policies, though it does not rely on a single legislative act specifically for this sector. The Higher Education Authority (HEA) has been instrumental in advancing gender equality, particularly through the HEA National Review of Gender Equality in Irish Higher Education Institutions (2016), which outlined key recommendations for improving gender balance and equality within academia. This led to the introduction of the HEA's Gender Equality Taskforce Action Plan (2018-2020), which included the Senior Academic Leadership Initiative (SALI) aimed at improving the representation of women in senior academic roles.

In addition, the HEA Act 2022 strengthens the HEA's authority in overseeing equality, diversity, and inclusion across higher education institutions, requiring them to publish annual statements on progress regarding equality and to ensure that institutional governing bodies promote gender balance.

Ireland does not have a mandatory Positive Action Plan (PAP) system like some EU countries, but it does actively promote gender equality plans (GEPs), especially in alignment with Horizon Europe requirements. Institutions engaging in EU-funded research must have a GEP in place. Irish universities and research-performing organizations have generally adopted GEPs to meet these obligations and to demonstrate commitment to equality, diversity, and inclusion (EDI) beyond compliance.

Unlike some other EU countries, Ireland integrates gender mainstreaming through a combination of sectoral guidelines, HEA monitoring, and voluntary Athena SWAN Charter participation. Since 2015, Irish higher education institutions have been required to hold at least a bronze Athena SWAN award to be eligible for certain research funding streams. This requirement has contributed to formalising gender equality structures and strategies across the sector.

However, challenges persist, particularly regarding the underrepresentation of women in senior leadership positions, work-life balance, and the need for sustainable institutional cultural change.

Munster Technological University (MTU)

Motto: Equity in Action, Inclusion by Design

The first Gender Equality Plan (GEP) for Munster Technological University (MTU) was developed as part of the university's successful application for the Athena Swan Bronze Award, officially awarded in

April 2024. The GEP forms a key pillar of MTU's ongoing commitment to promoting equality, diversity, and inclusion across all aspects of university life. The plan was designed to ensure that concrete actions were identified to advance gender equality, guided by the specific needs and context of MTU as a newly established multi-campus technological university.

The creation of the GEP was preceded by a thorough analysis of gender equality challenges within the institution. This diagnostic phase was carried out through the Athena Swan Self-Assessment Team (SAT) and supported by the Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion (EDI) Office. It was based on the collection and analysis of sex-disaggregated institutional data concerning staff and students, including recruitment, promotion, progression, leadership representation, and work-life balance. The diagnostic also incorporated qualitative insights gathered through staff and student surveys, focus groups, and wide consultations across campuses.

The resulting Gender Equality Plan, adopted in 2023, addresses multiple objectives: improving gender balance in decision-making bodies and leadership positions; enhancing gender equality in recruitment, career progression, and workload allocation; fostering a supportive and inclusive culture for all staff and students; and embedding EDI principles into MTU's institutional structures and practices. Particular attention is given to recognising the intersection of gender with other characteristics such as caring responsibilities, disability, ethnicity, and socio-economic background.

A distinctive feature of MTU's approach has been the participatory and collaborative nature of the GEP design. Staff and students from all parts of the university were actively engaged through workshops, consultations, and committee participation. The process was coordinated by the Athena Swan Self-Assessment Team, in cooperation with the EDI Committee, the EDI Office, senior management, and the wider MTU community. This inclusive approach ensured that the plan addressed both institutional and individual needs, while also fostering a sense of shared ownership of the GEP and its implementation.

In terms of implementation, the GEP outlines a series of structural and cultural measures. These include the introduction of transparent and formalised procedures for recruitment, promotion, and progression; the adoption of equitable workload allocation models; enhanced support for staff returning from family-related leave; and strengthened data collection systems to better monitor gender equality. Cultural measures include mandatory EDI and unconscious bias training for staff, awareness-raising campaigns, and actions to normalise gender equality as a shared institutional value.

The implementation of the GEP is overseen by the EDI Committee and the Athena Swan SAT, with responsibility for monitoring and evaluation assigned to the Executive Management Team and Governing Body. The GEP is strongly linked to MTU's Athena Swan Action Plan 2023–2027 and is considered a living document, regularly reviewed and updated to ensure it remains responsive to the evolving needs of the university community.

The GEP for MTU is available here: <https://www.mtu.ie/edi/>

3.4 National context: Spain

Spain, within the European context, ranks 4th according to the Gender Equality Index (1), with 76.7 points. This position has improved year after year, as seen on the index website, which has been measuring data since 2013 (referencing 2010), when Spain was ranked 7th with 66.4 points.

Regarding Spanish legislation, it is important to note that our country has delegated certain competencies to the autonomous communities, where agreements have been reached allowing these

regions to regulate their legislation, based on national and/or European laws, such as the case of Galicia.

With the enactment of Organic Law 3/2007, of March 22, for effective equality between women and men, Royal Decree 901/2020, and Royal Decree 902/2020, a cross-cutting dimension of equality is achieved, extending its reach across various areas of the legal framework.

At the business and collective bargaining level, Collective Agreements are agreements between employers and employee representatives that regulate labor conditions in various sectors or companies, and often include specific provisions to promote gender equality.

Additionally, in the scientific field, the report published in March 2025 by the Ministry of Science and Innovation, *Women in Science in Numbers*, is a reference. Its goal is to function as an analytical tool for gender inequalities in the Spanish scientific system, enabling the evaluation of advances and setbacks in closing the gender gap; to quickly and accurately understand the impact of our equality policies, and to provide an objective portrait of the participation and leadership of women researchers and scientists in universities, public research organizations, and Spanish companies.

The analysis of the presence and participation of female researchers in higher education and public research organizations in Spain reveals significant progress in incorporating women into the science and technology system, but also persistent gender gaps, particularly at the highest levels of the research career. In 2023, women represent 39.6% of the research staff in Spain, specifically making up 56% at early academic stages, but decreasing as they progress in their research careers.

At Grade A, corresponding to Full Professors, only 27.4% are women, although this figure has grown by 7.4 percentage points since 2012-2013. In pre-doctoral stages, women represent 47.1%, while in post-doctoral stages, they reach 52%. In Grade B, which includes Associate Professors, women make up 45.4%, indicating that, although progress has been made, there is still a glass ceiling in the transition to Full Professorship. The Glass Ceiling Index has improved in the past decade, moving from 1.73 in 2018-2019 to 1.57 in 2022-2023, suggesting that women's promotion is improving, but the scissors effect still persists, and thus the glass ceiling remains a structural barrier. Progress is very slow, and unfortunately, parity would take several decades to achieve in some areas, as projections suggest (e.g., in the Social Sciences and Humanities compared to Engineering and Technology (11%), for example).

One of the major national advances for promoting gender equality in R&D was the additional provision of Organic Law 2/2024 of August 1, on gender-balanced representation and presence in decision-making bodies. It outlines how merit evaluation, CVs, and research trajectories should be organized in public R&D&I calls.

CTAG- Galician Automotive Technology Centre

MOTTO: "GENDER EQUALITY PLAN: A Driving Force for Equality That Fuels the Future"

In accordance with Article 45 of Organic Law 3/2007, of March 22, for effective equality of women and men, the Center implemented a Gender Equality Plan in May 2012. One of the main milestones is to promote the adoption of concrete measures for gender equality within companies, requiring them to adopt measures aimed at eliminating obstacles and preventing any type of labor discrimination between sexes.

Currently, following the publication of Royal Decree-Law 6/2019, of March 1, on urgent measures to guarantee equal treatment and opportunities between women and men in employment, in companies with more than 50 workers, CTAG continues the commitment made in 2010 regarding the application

of equal treatment and opportunities between men and women, striving to eliminate sex-based discrimination and incorporating diversity into our values, applying it across the entire organization.

Under this regulation, the National Collective Agreement for the engineering and technical office sector stipulates, in Article 50, that labor relations must respect non-discrimination rules, with special mention to non-discrimination on the grounds of sex and the application of the Organic Law on Effective Equality Between Women and Men, fostering a culture of full respect for equality.

In line with this, for the negotiation of the Second Gender Equality Plan at CTAG, a negotiating committee was established in January 2024, and active work is ongoing to finalize the second Gender Equality Plan at CTAG. In connection with the current negotiations, and as per Regulation 902/2020, a wage audit and job valuation are carried out, which are two tools to analyze if there is any pay gap, and are appended to the diagnostic report under negotiation.

The implementation of equality at our center has brought improvements in all aspects. Additionally, as part of our strategic actions, CTAG has launched a series of socially impactful measures:

- Participation in the Inspira Steam program, a pioneering project aimed at encouraging young people's interest in science and technology, especially girls. This program is based on awareness-raising and guidance actions led by professionals, both women and men, from the fields of research, science, and technology. It is also innovative in incorporating group mentoring in initiatives to promote STEAM disciplines.
- Bringing science closer to girls by opening our facilities and celebrating International Day of Women and Girls in Science, which is observed worldwide on February 11.

Promotion of scientific challenge programs: Initiatives are promoted that reward projects incorporating a gender perspective in their design, such as the LPRODAYS program, organized in collaboration with the University of Vigo and the Faculty of Telecommunications.

3.5 National context: Serbia

According to the 2024 Global Gender Gap Report published by the World Economic Forum, Serbia ranks 26th out of 146 countries, with a score of 0.779 (on a scale where 1.0 denotes full parity). The strongest performance areas include educational attainment—where women consistently outperform men—and ministerial-level political representation. At the same time, the country continues to score lower in economic participation and opportunity, ranking approximately 77th globally in that pillar. In the United Nations Development Programme's Gender Inequality Index, Serbia ranks 35th worldwide, with an index value of 0.132, outperforming several countries in the region. At the national level, Serbia's Gender Equality Index, developed with support from the European Institute for Gender Equality, improved from 52.4 in 2016 to 58.0 in 2021, with the most progress seen in the area of political power. Nevertheless, systemic issues—particularly around economic empowerment, care burdens, and gender-based violence—continue to hinder Gender Equality.

The Constitution of Serbia (2006, 2021) explicitly guarantees “equality between women and men” and defines that the state is to develop “a policy of equal opportunities”(Article 15). It prohibits direct and indirect discrimination on various grounds, including gender (Article 21). The Law on Gender Equality (LGE), adopted in 2021, mandates equal opportunities in all spheres of public and private life, obliges public authorities and employers to implement gender equality measures, and introduces mechanisms such as gender-responsive budgeting, mandatory gender impact assessments of policies, including gender equality plans for larger public entities. The LGE explicitly mandates measures to ensure equal participation and non-discriminatory treatment, among other, in “science and technological

development, information-communication technologies and the information society”. Finally, the Law on Science and Research (2019) also defines, in Article 8, as one of its core principles, “Gender Equality in research and innovation, including in decision making bodies”.

In parallel, the Law on the Prohibition of Discrimination (2009) provides a comprehensive anti-discrimination framework, establishing the Commissioner for the Protection of Equality as an independent body tasked with addressing complaints and initiating proceedings. Labour legislation (2005, 2014 and 2018), further reinforces Gender Equality by prohibiting discrimination in employment, ensuring equal pay for equal work, and safeguarding maternity and parental rights. Additionally, the Family Law (2005) promotes equality in family relations and provides legal protections against domestic violence. The Law on the Prevention of Domestic Violence (2016) strengthens these protections by establishing urgent and preventive measures, mandating intersectoral cooperation, and focusing on victim safety and risk assessment. Serbia is also a party to key international treaties such as the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women and the Council of Europe’s Istanbul Convention. Institutional mechanisms supporting this legal framework include the Ministry for Human and Minority Rights and Social Dialogue, the Gender Equality Coordination Body, and the Parliamentary Committee on Human and Minority Rights and Gender Equality.

However, in practice, there are major legal barriers to the implementation of Gender Equality. Namely, the Constitutional Court of Serbia initiated, in June 2024, proceedings to assess the constitutionality of the LGE, based on the claim of legal inconsistencies or societal harm “stemming from provisions that could be deemed unconstitutional, particularly those concerning gender-sensitive language and related sanctions”. The primary concern cited by opponents—including some linguists, and institutions such as the Serbian Orthodox Church—relates to provisions enforcing mandatory use of gender-sensitive language in public documents, media, and educational materials. Critics argue that this concept of “gender-sensitive language” is not grounded in the standardized Serbian language system, lacks legal clarity, and is therefore incompatible with constitutional guarantees regarding legal certainty and freedom of expression. Following the Court’s order, public authorities and employers are temporarily relieved from obligations to adopt individual gender-equality measures and regulations prescribed by the LGE. The Constitutional Court has given the National Assembly’s Legislative Committee one month to submit its opinion on this matter, but no such opinion has been issued yet. Thus, until a final Court decision is issued, the LGE’s provisions remain dormant.

ETF - The School of Electrical Engineering of the University of Belgrade

Motto: "Empowering Equality, Leading in Tech."

The ETF is a top-tier educational and scientific institution in the field of electrical engineering and computer science. It offers BA, MS and PhD programmes which enrol more than 1,000 students each year. Equality of opportunities is core to the ETF mission and gender balance is a critical component for the ETF to ensure fair access and equity for its teaching, research, managerial and support staff. The ETF adopted its formal Gender Equality Plan (GEP) on July 4, 2022, making it one of the first Serbian higher-education institutions to do so. The plan was developed as part of the MINDtheGEPs project and tailored using institutional gender data specific to STEM fields and the faculty’s culture. The GEP focuses on enhancing gender balance in five main areas: 1) organizational culture and balance between professional and private life, 2) leadership structures and decision-making bodies, 3) employment, selection, appointments, and career progression, 4) representation in teaching and research activities, and 5) measures against gender based violence and sexual harassment. Priority actions in the GEP address: 1) Enhancing women’s participation in research and innovation, aiming to improve career progression and inclusion in research projects leadership, 2) Monitoring of gender composition in

academic and decision-making roles, using gender-disaggregated data gathering across departments, 3) Awareness-raising activities, including a dedicated webpage, workshops, and public communication by the ETF's leadership. For the implementation of its GEP, the ETF established a devoted core team composed by researchers and employees, external collaborators, and experts in Gender Equality. The appointment of female role models, notably including a first female Vice-Dean for Academic Affairs, was another steps forward in this regard. The Gender Equality Officer, within the Central Administration, was also appointed, with the role to provide advice on gender, inclusion, diversity management and sexual harassment prevention, and to coordinate the GEP implementation, monitoring and evaluation.

The ETF's GEP is available here:

https://www.etf.bg.ac.rs/uploads/files/Akta_fakulteta/Plan_za_postizanje_rodne_ravnopravnosti_v_2.pdf

4. Designing cultural and structural organisational change

4.1 Theoretical framework: fixing the system, not the women

Applying a feminist theoretical framework was a strategic choice in MINDtheGEPs. Feminist epistemologies (Harding 1986, Haraway 1988) serve as a reminder for the fact that the economic and political context in which Western science has developed has led to scientific paradigms and organisational cultures that perpetuate inequalities. This means that achieving equality requires not only welcoming more women in the sciences, but also a rethinking of how we do science and how it fits into our lives. It is not just about the numbers; we also need to change institutions and the knowledge system, allowing the pendulum to swing back and forth between culture and structure. Cultural actions are unlikely to succeed unless they are accompanied by structural actions, which in MINDtheGEPs meant taking the role of both cultural and material dimensions within social processes into account on the micro, meso and macro levels, and acknowledging the fact that gender is a social structure that is characterized by multiple intersected barriers, which in turn requires multiple intersected actions to be removed (Acker 2009, Connell 1987, Risman 2018).

Applying a 'women approach' emphasises the systemic disadvantage that women face in comparison to men. This perspective sheds light on the barriers to women's participation in the labour market, politics, and decision-making processes and examines measures to reduce discrimination such as implementing gender quotas and promoting work-life balance initiatives (Kantola and Lombardo, 2017). This approach fails to address inequalities while neglecting to address the deeper social structures, discriminatory norms and social practices at play, assuming a 'fixing the women' lens (Schiebinger, 2021). Additionally, the current dictat "publish or perish" (Weisshaar, 2017) imposes detrimental effects on individuals of all genders, across various scientific disciplines, prioritizing quantity over quality in research output.

MINDtheGEPs aims to fix the system, not the women. The aim goes beyond increasing the number of women. Instead, we aimed to change the way science and academic endeavors are experienced and undertaken. Instead of *fixing women* by asking them (and other marginalized groups) to conform to existing structures for advancement, MINDtheGEPs advocates for *fixing the system*; urging institutions to adapt to individuals in order to promote well-being, and science that is truly inclusive and beneficial for the community. We believe that excellent researchers and scientists are not who

adhere to the *unconditional worker model* sacrificing their personal lives under constant pressure. Neither the excellent and innovative institutions are not necessarily those that produce the highest number of publication. From this point-of-view, 'gendering' the sciences is not only about broadening and diversifying the range of individuals who conduct and disseminate research. It also requires the adoption of alternative models, based on cooperation (rather than competition), coexistence and intersectionality (as opposed to *trade-offs* between different aspects of one's life). By encouraging more diverse research teams – and leadership – we are able to offer a wider range of perspectives: not just in terms of research content, but also in the ways we do science, how we define excellence, and how we make recruitment and promotion processes work. This way, the results of efforts to promote gender equality can be more innovative, and bring benefit for many.

What fixing the system entails:

- Rethinking how we do science
- Changing the institutions
- Changing the knowledge system
- Applying feminist epistemologies
- Moving beyond seeing gender as equivalent to sex, viewing it as both 'regime' and a social structure, characterized by multiple intersected barriers and lines of inequality
- Applying an intersectional approach
- Ascribing value to caring and organisational work (often referred to as 'academic housework') and make it visible
- Bringing down the ideal of the 'devoted and unconditional worker' that harms not only women but also men and the entire organization

What fixing the women entails:

- Stopping at welcoming more women into the field
- Leaving (national) evaluation systems unchanged
- Reinforcing quantitative criteria for selection and recruitment
- Perceiving merit and excellence as neutral
- Only providing measures to compensate for motherhood penalty
- Excluding men from the target of measures
- Only focusing on sex and gender, forgetting to acknowledge racialization processes, sexual orientation, age, class, religion and disability.
- Only valorizing publications, not including networking and teaching
- Working overtime and/or asking colleagues to do overtime in the evening hours, during weekends and holidays

Table 2. Want to learn more about our theoretical framework?

- Acker, J. (2009). Gendered Institutional Theory: Sex Roles and Gendered Institutions. *American Journal of Sociology*, 91, 759-799.
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- Schiebinger, L. (2021). Gendered Innovations: integrating sex, gender, and intersectional analysis into science, health & medicine, engineering, and environment. *Tapuya: Latin American Science, Technology and Society*, 4(1).
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4.2 Model framework: the MINDtheGEPs approach to evidence-based policies for gender equality plans

A stepwise approach to gender equality

Gender equality changes over time, and so should the plan: an ongoing process for improving gender equality. The European Institute for Gender Equality’s definition states that providing a tailored GEP requires defining a process aimed at achieving gender equality by identifying specific organisations’ needs.

“An effective GEP should be founded on a model of change that identifies the problems it seeks to address, their causes and desired outcomes, including targets; it should detail the set of activities that are required to achieve the aims, and indicators to monitor progress. A GEP should engage the whole organisation, from senior leaders to staff, students (in the case of a teaching organisation) and stakeholders, and it should form an ongoing process that encourages self-reflection and review of processes and practices”. (EU, 2021)

The lifecycle of a typical GEP is a circular and iterative process consisting of five consecutive phases:

1. *audit*, (collection of data, review of existing practices, analysis of law) it’s the diagnosis phase, where sex-disaggregated data is collected);
2. *planning* (identification of targets and allocation of resources, activities to achieve objectives, needs and concerns are defined);
3. *implementation* (planned activities start to build capacity and support);
4. *monitoring* (pay attention to process and progresses of the implemented activities and measure their);
5. *impact and evaluation* (evaluate and ensure the sustainability of the implemented GEP, and refining starting from the top, as a circular and iterative process, ongoing review of findings and progresses).

A GEP should be the result of a reflection of all employees concerning crucial areas for the wellbeing of women, men (and hopefully of all minoritised subjectivities present) of all levels, roles, profiles, type of contract (full-term, part-time, permanent, fixed term).

Establishing governance structures

Functional and recognised governance structures are essential for the implementation of measures and plans to effectively lead structural change. In MINDtheGEPs, partners set up several governance structures with clearly defined mandates, roles, and responsibilities:

- *A board responsible for implementing the GEP* (Gender Equality Plan Implementing Board and similar structures):
- *Network of representatives from different departments* (Delegates Network, or similar representative bodies of complex organizational structures)
- *Gender equality manager*
- *Gender database manager*

Steps for setting up a GEP

In the EIGE approach, GEPs should:

1. be formal public documents, signed by the institution's top management, and demonstrate a clear commitment to gender equality
2. have dedicated resources (staff and funds) for design, implementation and monitoring
3. include arrangements for data collection and monitoring that assure the GEP is based on evidence, and sex (or gender) disaggregated data
4. be supported by training and capacity building activities.

In addition to these mandatory process-related requirements, the European Commission requires that GEPs address (at minimum) following five thematic areas: 1) work-life balance and organisational culture; 2) gender balance in leadership and decision-making; 3) gender equality in recruitment and career progression; 4) integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content; and 5) measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment (European Commission 2021b, p. 13). The GEP architecture rests on three pillars: **data collection**, **monitoring**, and **training**, requiring cross-thematic and complex actions across all five areas.

Data collection and monitoring system

Policy cannot address and solve problems without clear and defined knowledge of the situation that the policy is meant to fix. That requires issue-specific data. For GEPs, the evidence-base should be sex- or gender-disaggregated baseline data for all staff categories. Data can help unveil existing differences between women and men in different roles and levels. Data can also reflect the organisation, describing the personnel and their skills, the research and teaching performance, the ability for outreach, the success in attracting skills and funding, as well as the relations and agreements with the local and national industrial system.

Table 3. Data, no problem, no policy!

- GEPs are strategic policy documents
- Design your GEP based on evidence, such as facts and figures
- Make sure you operate under the assumption that, without data, there will be no policy

Why should we collect data? Sex and gender variables in data collection can support:

1. The establishment of a baseline for mapping gender inequalities within the organisation and serving as a benchmark for evaluating structural and cultural improvements;
2. Gender equality analysis to identify strengths and weaknesses in the organisation, and help define actions in line with the organisation's priorities;
3. Monitoring to guide and adjust the GEP process and evaluate progress;
4. Communication to staff, students, other key stakeholders, and the wider public about the organisation's commitment to gender equality and the progress made.

Using data to assess inequalities: Gender inequalities within an organisation are not always obvious at first glance. The challenge is not only to identify the number of men and women in each role or part of the organisational structure, but also to highlight potential inequalities in all activities carried out by the organisation itself: research and teaching, but also in more political, managerial, and administrative tasks.

Applying a stepwise approach

We recommend structuring the efforts in accordance with the five key areas suggested by the European Commission, using a five-step approach:

Step 1: setting up a working group with experts. Ensure resources are made available and decide who carries out the initial assessment. If your organisation doesn't have a person or body responsible for gender equality, start by identifying the available expertise to support the assessment from a theoretical point of view (gender and organisational sociology, data analysis), and consider including heads of administrative offices that already collect the data we are interested in (this will open an ongoing dialogue with data providers), expertise from outside the organisation. Since much of the data that will be processed are personal and particular in nature, the inclusion of the data protection officer can help ensure compliance from the very beginning of the process. Moreover, an official mandate to perform the initial assessment is essential for success.

Step 2: mapping data and identifying providers. Assessment requires available data, but organisations are not always collecting data from a gender perspective, and the data is not always structured in queryable databases. Mapping is essential before starting the assessment, creating a list of data that (1) can be processed immediately; (2) need time to be systematised and then analysed; (3) are not present or accessible from a gender perspective and therefore require joint work with the administrative offices to be usable (e.g., restructuring databases and the way data are collected through new internal procedures to fill the information gap).

Step 3: create a vision. Very often, data are not collected by a single office. Each aspect of an RPO's activity has its own method of data collection and a database in which the data are organised, serving administrative and management purposes. These different systems, however, are not always interlinked and do not serve gender analysis purposes. However, data collected and systematised from a gender perspective can enable the central administration to plan internal policies on all work aspects not necessarily related to gender inequalities only. One challenge convincing the top management that a gender assessment is useful. Providing a strategic vision can be useful for getting management involved: illustrating the potential of this data for improving effectiveness and efficiency.

Step 4: design the context analyses. Before starting the assessment, make sure you have knowledge of the European and national legislative framework concerning gender equality and non-discrimination is useful. Here, the five key areas can provide the framework for the initial assessment. Mapping creates a top-down snapshot of the organisation that will serve as the basis for defining the GEP's objectives and actions. However, if information is missing, you can apply a bottom-up approach to supplement the data e.g., an. An online survey addressed to all employees can supplement aspects that are not captured from a gender perspective; i correct information that has been incorrectly recorded; i collect information on temporary staff; and collect information on the organisational culture (e.g. the presence of gender stereotypes, perceptions on success factors in the career, opinions on the organisation). Here, the Gender Equality Audit and Monitoring (GEAM) tool and the UniSAFE project offer support on both content and technical aspects.

Step 5: carrying out the assessment of gender inequalities/Imbalances. Data collection can be extremely time-consuming. It is t important to plan the actions well, and fit them to the available human resource. Once the data collection phase has been completed, the assessment can be carried out through descriptive statistics and describing the results. If some specific aspects are not captured through administrative data or a quantitative questionnaire, this can be complemented with interviews or focus groups to bridge information gaps. Benchmarking against other similar organisations in your country, or aggregated national statistics (e.g. SheFigures or the EIGE databases) can also serve as a reference context.

Fixing the GEP priorities, defining SMART indicators, monitoring and evaluating process and results

Once the data has been analysed, it is possible to identify the **strengths and weaknesses of the organisation** along with gender imbalances that are relevant to address in a context-sensitive GEP. From here, you will be able to define a list of areas where gender balance can be improved, and identify priority elements. This exercise allows the objectives and related actions of the GEP to be clearly formulated, as well as the time frame in which they should be placed and implemented.

Data flow and its relations: The initial assessment will produce a knowledge base and a point-of-departure. Data will most likely be missing in the first assessment, hence we propose to **expand the data collection every year**. Implement procedures to make data collection and analysis as automatic as possible, ensuring a constant flow of data from the relevant offices to the group in charge of the process. **data should collected and published annually**. Collecting data on an annual basis allows the monitoring process to start at the same time as the GEP is implemented, and provide guidance. There is partial overlap between the gender data assessment and Gender Budgeting, a process that provides

a more static overview of the organisation's situation at a certain date (often 31 December). Gender budgets are commonly drafted every two years, whereas the assessment required for the GEP is updated annually, and provides much more detailed information that feeds into the GEP's own monitoring process. If the GEP's actions have a real impact, changes will be recorded by Gender Budgeting, which will track changes over time. Conversely, the main results of Gender Budgeting will allow the organisation to update, enrich and modify the GEP because they will be part of the evaluation of the Plan itself, creating a continuous process that should be strengthened over time.

Capturing data about the factors that shape gender inequalities: Gender is a social structure characterized by multiple intersected barriers, which in turn requires multiple intersected actions to be removed. This means that we need several types of data to be able to capture the various push and pull factors that (de)construct gender inequalities in the early-, middle-, and late stages of research careers, on the (individual (micro), organizational (meso), and national or cultural (macro) level.

Table 4. Checklist for collecting data

- Remember that GEPs are strategic documents: design your GEP on evidence, facts and figures
- Operate under the assumption that without data, there will be no policy
- Use data to assess inequalities and identify gaps by capturing data about the factors that shape gender inequalities on the micro, meso, and macro levels
- Make sure you collect data that is disaggregated by sex and gender
- Complement with data about gender identity and include a third category for non-binary (when possible and in accordance with legal requirements)
- Structure your work following the five key areas suggested by the European Commission
- Define your priorities, define indicators, monitor, and evaluate the process and results
- Avoid “fixing the women” by focusing on increasing the numbers
- Make sure the GEP actions have a broad focus (it is not just about increasing the number of women in different fields)
- Include diversity management

5. Sustaining change

The main challenges to ensuring sustainability are related to funding, budget allocation, and time. Having experts within the organisation is not sufficient, as key decisions are often made elsewhere. To achieve real and lasting change, sustainability efforts require a strategically positioned role dedicated to coordination — for instance, a gender officer embedded at an institutional level. However, enthusiasm alone does not equate to commitment; it must be supported by an allocated budget and formal authority.

For meaningful transformation to occur, four elements are essential: (1) bottom-up approaches that foster participation and ownership; (2) strategic alliances with experts; (3) the systematic use of data as evidence; and (4) the active engagement of decision-makers. While funding enables a wide range of activities, the longevity of any initiative depends on the integration of gender equality actions into the organisation's overall strategy.

Moreover, institutional approaches must consider national cultural and political contexts. Political and legal frameworks can serve as important **drivers** by providing legitimacy, mandates, and accountability mechanisms for gender equality. However, they may also act as **barriers** when existing regulations are fragmented, outdated, or inconsistently enforced, or when political priorities shift away from equality objectives. Recognising both the enabling and constraining dimensions of these contexts is therefore crucial to designing sustainable and adaptive gender strategies.

Sustainable success requires strong relationships between unions, management, and leadership, as well as alignment with legal requirements. Organisational culture and structure should be strategically leveraged to frame gender equality as a long-term goal and as a metric of institutional excellence. Importantly, culture and structure can evolve from within.

To this end, we recommend building alliances with three key groups: (1) gender and equality experts, (2) men as allies and advocates, and (3) students as change agents. These groups should be actively engaged from the outset to ensure inclusivity and shared ownership of initiatives.

Finally, effective communication is crucial. While it may be easier to rely on existing networks, potential allies can often be found in unexpected places. We therefore recommend promoting transparency through open calls across the organisation and formalising internal networks for communication and dissemination, ensuring that information and opportunities reach all institutional levels.

More strategic actions and tactic in achieving sustainability could be found in the MINDtheGEPs report D8.4 – Sustainability plan.

5.1 Governance and monitoring

Monitoring and evaluation are an integral part of any process of change, allowing organisations to assess effectiveness. Having a monitoring and evaluation strategy in place makes it possible to monitor and support the process of implementing gender equality plans, thus increasing the impact. However, effective monitoring and evaluation requires careful planning to make sure it fits within the GEP architecture.

Table 5. Monitoring and evaluation - the basic concepts

Monitoring is a continuous process, in which data is systematically collected in order to provide management and key stakeholders with regular updates on the progress and achievement of objectives and the use of allocated funds.

Evaluation relates to a systematic and objective assessment of an ongoing or completed project, programme or policy based on the monitoring data, providing lessons learnt for the planning of future measures.

Monitoring ensures that we focus on the right thing, targeting the *implementation* of a gender equality plan. Evaluation, on the other hand, ensures we achieve the right outcomes and is focused on the strategic level, i.e. *the impact or outcome* that we want the GEP to achieve.

They have different time frames: monitoring happens on an ongoing basis, and records the progress of each action, while evaluation happens at the end of the GEP life-cycle, and requires a more in-depth analysis.

Source: Taking a reflexive approach to gender equality for institutional transformation, report from the TARGET project (<https://www.gendertarget.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/08/D4.1-Monitoring-tool.pdf>)

Developing strategy for monitoring and evaluation

Monitoring starts with selecting indicators, provided by the offices and bodies responsible for carrying out the actions, and the databases used for the initial assessment. To ensure monitoring happens in a structured way, it may be useful to set up monitoring sessions with the offices and bodies connected to the plan. This kind of regular scheduled meetings can serve both to reduce workload and increase engagement. When it comes to evaluation, it is important to take a close look at the organisational context (available from the original assessment), monitoring reports, gender budgets. To go beyond

quantitative aspects, we recommend also using qualitative data (e.g. focus groups or interviews with key groups or roles in the organization) to explore the impact on the structural and cultural levels.

Communicating results

Communication is an integral part of evaluation, and plays an important role in (potential) structural and cultural change. Reports should be disseminated through official documents and become available through the organization's website, along with the results of the final evaluation. Continuous communication can also help make leaders part of the process of change, by ensuring that top-level management receives regular updates on both progress and challenges through regular meeting structures (with ad hoc meetings if need be). Moreover, both progress and the final evaluation should be shared with different stakeholders and departments, to secure their engagement and support for different activities and measures. Finally, communication can help set the stage for a new GEP lifecycle that allows us to improve, and close any remaining gaps that have become visible through available data, negotiations within the organisation, and the process of implementing actions, monitoring and evaluation.

Developing a system for monitoring and evaluation

In MINDtheGEPs, monitoring and evaluation setted up a system for all seven organisations with three cornerstones:

- Looking at evaluation as a proactive, non judgemental, support activity
- Looking at evaluation as non-linear implementation process
- Focusing on the iterative nature of evaluation

This allowed the project to deal with complexity, , develop long-term relationships between evaluators and project or programme staff. With ongoing evaluation is ongoing, we were able to manage continous feedback in a way that helped support learning and decision-making. This approach is particularly appropriate for programmes working in complex or uncertain environments, or in situations that require collaboration between many different stakeholders from different organisaitons or sectors.

Table 6. Monitoring and evaluation: what to consider

Monitoring and evaluation supports self-reflexivity through participative evaluation efforts. It can also contribute to:

- **Quality control:** providing structures to oversee the action flow, control compliance and adherence with main evaluation criteria
- **Problem solving:** identifying and overcoming obstacles, and facilitating mitigation

Develop good indicators

- Make sure you have a baseline that can be used for comparison at different intervals.
- Use both quantitative and qualitative indicators

Assess four dimensions of plans and actions:

- How **effective** is the action: does it achieve its objectives? -
- How **relevant** is the action: is it dynamic) it is related to different dimensions of change and negotiation? (interpretive, symbolic, institutional, operational)
- Is the **impact** objective (measurable short term changes) or subjective (building on consensus)
- Is the activity **sustainable**: did the change become a permanent part of the organisation, with resources allocated?

5.2 Training, awareness and communication

Awareness of inequality is at the core of the “no data no policy” principle. Proactive communication, dissemination and training activities have played a key role in supporting cultural change, and the data collected across organisations have helped pinpoint both actions for the GEPs, and informed the efforts to design different efforts to raise awareness.

Training

In MINDtheGEPs, efforts were made to ensure the consortium had the capacity to raise awareness. Training is one of the most effective tools to raise and increase awareness and sensitivity about gender equality, diversity and inclusion. MINDtheGEPs used a “train the trainers” approach, delivered workshops with trainers from organisations across the project, followed by training within the different organisations. Training should be designed to “fix the system”, not the women, which means training should include *everyone*, not focus on only women, or only early career researchers.

In MINDtheGEPs, we have worked in line with the three principles outlined in the EIGEs gender equality training toolkit, stressing the importance of e1) engaging the whole organisation, 2) assessing training on evidence-based organisational needs, and 3) creating an ongoing and long-term process.

In order to guarantee that actions are feasible, it is important to identify:

- **Who is leading the work** (department and/or individuals), who supports the work, which part of the organisation is responsible for training employees, and if there is a gender equality office/officer in the organisation.
- **Who the training is for** (management, manager and leaders, researchers and teachers, administrative and technical staff)
- **The human resources:** identifying trainers is part of developing a training plan.
- **The economic resources:** making sure that there is a devoted budget for training activities.

Gender equality training programmes can comprise a wide range of educational tools and processes: face-to-face training; staff induction programmes, online modules, guidance materials and compendia of resources, networks for sharing expertise. Regardless of format, the best approach is to integrate training into existing training plans. This requires:

- **Identifying the training needs for different groups**, for example through surveys in the organisation, focusing on basic concepts of gender equality and gender stereotypes; design, methods and techniques for the implementing plans, and the gender dimension in research projects in different STEM and SSH disciplines.
- Identifying **trainers**, for example by inviting staff who are already providing training for the organisation to express interest. However, in some cases you might need to look for expertise outside the organisation.
- Implement a **system for accreditation** and/or reward participation i
- **Make sure dates are in the calendar**, for example by making sure training is part of the annual planning of courses for staff.
- **Consider using a “train-the-trainers” approach**, building competence on gender equality that can benefit the organisation in the long term.

Table 7. Tips for organising training

- Start from your needs: look at the data first
- Organise training within the framework of existing meeting schedules
- Develop training in collaboration between your organisation and external experts
- Pay for external speakers: it helps you establish the idea that this is important
- Tailor your training to the organisation, and the audience
- Evaluate training in a way that covers critical areas that can help improve the next training cycle
- Provide different training for different staff categories
- Educate recruiters
- Include training in the GEP
- Integrate it in the organisations' training curriculum
- Make training mandatory (e.g. part of onboarding programmes)

In MINDtheGEPs, we organised two different trainings: the **EmpowLAB**, addressing the 'leaky pipeline' providing training for early career researchers, with particular focus on women. Here, the aim was to support career progression through reinforcement of research skills. Despite the focus on women, the training has been extended to men, and included PhD students, post-docs and temporary assistant professors in academia, and early to mid-career in organisations outside academia. The **BreakTopLAB** (Breaking Stereotypes at the Top Laboratory) on the other hand, addressed cultural aspects, which requires reaching individuals at various levels in the organisation. One key component is to educate and 'sensitize' individuals who have roles that give the influence, for example through membership in decision-making bodies and committees responsible for recruitment, promotions, and/or allocation of funds. The training was designed to raise awareness about the existence and significance of gender (im)balances, challenge preconceived notions about their origins, and engage in discussions to explore potential solutions. The central idea is to break gender stereotypes in selection processes by creating awareness about gender gaps in recruitment, promotion, decision-making, research programmes and funding, along with the underlying mechanisms at the micro, meso and macro level, with a particular focus on unconscious gender bias in procedures and criteria used to evaluate merit and excellence.

Table 8. Developing and providing training

- **Start by mapping the stakeholders** and make sure you engage the right people in the design of training and dissemination.
- **Make the gender training plan part of the official training programme** by integrating it into the organisation's training plan. If possible, make it mandatory and a part of your onboarding activities.
- **Exchange knowledge with similar organisations**, learn from others, collaborate, and share experience.
- **Make sure your training activities address the whole organisation**, and include messages that resonate with & can engage different groups.
- **When you have a training plan, make sure it is communicated** and available in the obvious places where staff would look.

Communication

In the very beginning of the project, all partners received communications training, and communication experts from Uppsala University have been supporting the project along the way, using a storytelling approach to capture the different journeys, and packaging recommendations and good practice from the project in a series of briefs and “Open Forum” discussions. Meanwhile, partners have designed communication activities based on what has been the best fit for their needs.

Organisational culture is transmitted through communication. This means that having a communications strategy and plan is a key factor for success. Communication can help raise awareness, generate interest, facilitate engagement, develop buy-in to actions and create a readiness to implement.

Raise awareness and make (in)equality visible

When launching the GEP project, awareness raising and engagement from all parts of the organisation is important, as is debunking the belief that equality is a “women’s affair”. There are several ways this can be done:

- Build your reputation in the organisation!
- Make sure your communications (and activities) address both men and women.
- Involve both men and women, and ensure you have support from all parts of the organisation.
- Use colleagues as advocates and allies, to disseminate information, promote activities and encourage engagement.
- Increase the visibility of the results of our efforts through targeted communications, i.e. public events, online information, and/or print materials with key messages.
- Adapt your communication to the audience. Different generations communicate in different ways: want to reach early career researchers and students? Make sure you pick formats and channels that resonate with them!
- Make women visible! Ask a woman to deliver a keynote address at important events.
- Develop awareness raising activities, for example workshops or seminars.
- Offer something to encourage participation: food and drink, or issue a certificate of attendance!
- Involve stakeholders outside your organisations: they can provide a fresh (bias free) eye on your efforts, inspiration, serve as role models, and motivate.

Table 9. Developing a communications strategy and plan

Make sure that you:

- **Start by mapping stakeholders and gatekeepers**, and make sure you engage the right people in the design of your communications strategy and plan.
- **Tailor your messages for different audiences and target specific groups**: A message meant for researchers might not be relevant for technical and administrative staff.
- **Raise awareness about inequalities and offer a solution** by showing how you contribute to solving the problem.
- **Find out where your audience is** and make sure you are visible where others can see you: attend meetings that are already in people’s calendars, and use existing channels (e.g. internal newsletters and intranet, and external channels like public websites and social media to reach both staff and publics), and make sure you provide access to information through dedicated web pages for staff, and that the work is made visible at high profile events.
- **Use both informal and formal channels**: Try to be where the decisions are made.
- **Try to get men involved** as advocates and allies.
- **Leverage champions/advocates** to deliver your messages and prepare the ground/engage their peers. Engage people in different roles and positions of influence, who are good leaders/role models, and ask them to help draw attention to your practices.
- **Allow people to contribute and co-create**: Make engagement part of your communication strategy, for example by organising meetings or webinars where participants can flag issues and give feedback, and provide ways to communicate ideas (e.g. suggestion boxes or feedback surveys after events).
- **Communicate your results** and make sure you give something back to contributors: Inform both about meetings and outcomes

Avoid some of the obvious traps:

- **Don’t decide on the form before knowing what you want to achieve**: sometimes an email to the right person is more effective than a cool video or a colourful print leaflet.
- **Don’t send the wrong message**: if you say that activities are not compulsory, the risk is that people think that what you are doing is not that important.

6. Working with the key areas

6.1 Work-life balance and organisational culture

In promoting gender equality, it is essential to support the "dual-earner dual-carer" model, which entails encouraging both parents, particularly fathers, in heterosexual parental relationships, to balance family and work responsibilities. This approach challenges the traditional assumption of the "unconditional researcher worker," fostering a more inclusive environment where caregiving is recognized as a shared responsibility.

Moreover, supporting caregivers in their professional journeys is vital for creating a fair work culture. Organizations should prioritize measures that facilitate work-life balance, such as a Parents’ Travel Grant, a reassessment of duties after parental leave, and formal recognition of the time dedicated to caregiving. To effectively advocate for these changes, it is crucial to possess a thorough understanding of the issues at hand. This includes presenting objective, reliable, and verifiable evidence regarding

how caregiving responsibilities impact the academic careers of women, particularly in terms of mobility, productivity, and promotion, often referred to as the motherhood penalty.

Additionally, it is important to analyze who the beneficiaries of these measures would be and to compile a list of best practices that have already been implemented. Identifying the offices where relevant decisions are made will allow for targeted negotiations with leadership, ensuring that work-life balance initiatives are effectively integrated into the organizational culture.

We recommend that you:

- Break down the “unconditional worker” assumption and support the “dual-earner dual-career” model. How? Negotiate with leadership for work-life balance measures, inform parents about their rights (and don’t forget the fathers!), and make sure you provide information (by setting up a webpage dedicated to work-family balance), and install changing tables in men’s bathrooms
- Know the issue: You need to have a detailed grasp of the problem that the measure you are advocating for addresses: demonstrating relatively objective, reliable and verifiable evidence on the impact of caring responsibilities on academic careers of women, including their mobility, productivity and promotion (e.g. motherhood penalty); using (finding) relevant data from your organisation. That entails analysing who the beneficiaries would be, having a list of already introduced best practices, and identifying where the relevant decisions are being made and, therefore, with whom to negotiate
- Remember that rights are different in different countries, and for different roles and positions in your organisation. Make sure you design measures that work for those who are in the weakest positions (taking power relations into account). And connect your measures to the organisational, national, and/or international legal provisions and policies (e.g. GEP; EU Directive (2019/1158) on work-life balance for parents and carers.
- Articulate gains and harms: point to tangible benefits that adoption of the proposed measure would have on the beneficiaries, all employees (including men), and the organisation as a whole. Point to negative impacts that would result from inaction, and collect evidence on the positive results of implementing advocated measures elsewhere.
- Be clear about the aim and consult with relevant stakeholders (people directly affected by the issue you are working on), e.g., which expenses could be covered, and which duties could be reduced after returning from parental leave.
- Bear in mind that there are different profiles: we often think about teaching and research, but there are also technical and administrative staff, who have different career paths and working conditions, and those roles facilitate research and education. Different legal frameworks govern their professional roles.
- Build alliances across the organisation.
- Monitor and evaluate your work.
- Communicate about your efforts, and think about the language you use: we need to balance inclusion against effective communication. Make sure your message is clear to everyone!

Table 10. Setting up a webpage dedicated to work-family balance

One way employers can support work-life balance is by providing information that parents need to plan and divide care responsibilities.

- Have you collected national provisions/ policies on work-family balance?
- Have you verified the availability of work-family balance tools in your organisation (e.g. flexible working arrangements, family room, nursery, additional health insurance, etc)
- Have you collected the procedures, links, descriptions, and documents/forms required to apply for different benefits and leave?
- Have you provided accessible and comprehensible descriptions of maternity/paternity/family leave procedures, rights, and obligations of employees being on leave, and the impact of leaves on career development? Or have you collected all the necessary links to the description of these procedures?
- Have you provided accessible and comprehensive descriptions of maternity/paternity/family leave procedures, rights, and obligations of employees on leave and the impact of leaves on career development? Or have you collected all necessary links to the description of these procedures?
- Have you provided accessible and comprehensible descriptions of maternity/paternity/family leave procedures, rights, and obligations of employees on leave and the impact of leave on career development? Or have you collected all necessary links to the description of these procedures?
- Are there work-family facilities such as family rooms, nurseries, kindergartens, sport centres, etc. at your organization (e.g., on a university campus)
- Have you grouped available policies, tools, and procedures into wider categories, e.g. childcare, elderly care, health issues, leisure time, etc?
- Have you collected contact information from all departments responsible for work-family measures?
- Have you decided where the webpage will be located (e.g., as a tab available from the organisational main page or as a subpage of an individual department/office)
- Have you contacted the web page administrator?

6.2 Gender balance in leadership and decision making

Most leaders are men. Sexist stereotypes and biases perpetuate this, which is why women often choose not to pursue leadership positions. The pervasive belief that masculine traits are required for effective leadership is a significant barrier for women. Additionally motherhood and caregiving responsibilities affect women's career trajectories greatly, which cannot be explained by maternity leave alone. In MINDtheGEPs, we have focused on three things to provide actionable measures for research organizations to create a fairer and more inclusive leadership environment.

1. Challenging gender stereotypes about leadership.
2. Promoting comprehensive gender awareness training, revising and diversifying selection criteria.
3. Enhancing the visibility of successful women.

MINDtheGEP's has advocated for inclusive training programs for all, to promote gender equality in decision-making and leadership. Comprehensive gender awareness training facilitates smoother implementation of initiatives and fosters understanding among employees. Data shows strong support for awareness measures. There are different strategies for preparing training for organisational change processes.

- Bottom-up approaches start from the grassroots of the organisations and move up the management ladder.
- Top-down approaches target management first and trickles down.

To achieve gender equality in leadership and decision-making, we recommend that you consider a holistic approach. Implementing a strategic plan that utilizes multiple tools simultaneously, such as

meetings, analyses, awareness measures, and recruitment efforts, can accelerate progress towards objectives. While not all organizations may be prepared for such extensive changes, it can be one of the quickest ways to achieve results.

- Prepare for the unexpected. Teaching & research routines may put some obstacles in the process of structural and leadership changes. In addition, decision-making on the senior management level is not always as democratic as that of smaller teams.
- Be helpful, not obstructive All interventions should be consistent with the academic life cycle, referring to national law and local regulations and policies.
- Knowledge is key. Keep in mind that academics and professionals, as well as middle and top management may not be gender sensitive. Thus, efforts to raise their awareness and build competencies need to be made. The more people in an organization that are gender-sensitive, the easier it will be for them to move towards structural change.
- Explore the culture of your organization. For example, staff working in STEM fields have their own culture with its own characteristics. STEM professionals and disciplines usually rely on numbers, data and direct outcomes. They might not be savvy in the social sciences which can make it challenging to grasp issues of gender sensitivity and equality. Capacity-building, competence-building, or awareness raising activities could follow an outcome-based approach. Explore non-traditional training forms.

Table 11. How to challenge stereotypes about leadership

Inspiring women to pursue positions of responsibility is crucial. One effective strategy is showcasing the achievements of successful women across diverse professional domains, offering inspiration and encouragement. By highlighting diverse examples of successful women, organizations can foster a culture that encourages women to aspire to leadership roles.

- Utilize data to highlight gender disparities in leadership roles.
- Promote diversity management and leadership initiatives.
- Encourage women to apply for decision-making positions.
- Foster an inclusive environment conducive to women's leadership.
- Provide tools for structural change to achieve gender equality in leadership
- Emphasize gender-neutral leadership qualities.
- Mitigate the impact of motherhood penalties.
- Implement mentorship programs to support women's career advancement.
- Ensure mentors are committed to supporting mentees' development. This commitment maximizes learning opportunities, enhances mentees' confidence, and facilitates career advancement in supportive environments.
- Learn from successful programs such as AKKA (a programme, launched in 2004 by Lund University as an attempt to raise gender knowledge and awareness and provide methods and tools for structural change in leadership positions).

Table 12. Using positive actions as a tool

Positive action is controversial, and includes gender quotas and economic incentives. There are three general pathways to implement positive action: through legislation, enforced by academic institutions, or mandated by research funding organisations. When positive action is used, attention to the context is key. Otherwise, you run the risk of implementing actions that turn out to be ineffective. Quotas can be used in recruitment, to steer the composition of evaluation committees, and to guide the allocation of research grants and fellowships.

Quotas can be used to mitigate unconscious biases inherent in review processes. Studies revealing discrimination against women during the review process provide support for quotas. Quotas can also increase the applicant pool, reflecting diverse perspectives and backgrounds (non-neutrality and positioning in research). Moreover, ensuring equal success rates regardless of gender sends a positive message to underrepresented groups, potentially boosting application rates. In addition, making women in senior academic roles more visible can inspire female students and young researchers and have a “role model effect.”

Quotas can help organisations overcome cultural and material limits to participation in cases where other inclusive recruitment strategies are not in place

6.3 Gender equality in recruitment and career progression

We recommend that you take an intersectional perspective, focus on consensus building and approach gender equality from a cross-sectional point of view. This will help generate buy-in from more groups. A holistic approach is needed to address more than one policy simultaneously, and promote a cultural shift within organisations.

- Communicate the fact that equality is not a zero-sum exercise, we are adding value
- Pay attention to recruitment, and look at the composition of evaluation teams
- Pay attention to the allocation of research grants and fellowships, and ensure the selection process is transparent
- Pay attention to traditional career advancement models: they might hide gender bias, and they might be different for researchers and technical/administrative staff
- Look at the criteria you use to evaluate performance and merit; some of the work women often do is undervalued in formal evaluations, gender balance can contribute to excellence; address bias related to factors like international mobility; and learn from examples of successful revisions to selection criteria, such as those at Mondragon Unibertsitatea.
- Promote gender-neutral (non-sexist) selection processes through inclusive job design and transparent practices.
- Consider financial incentives, for example, rewarding increased recruitment of women for leadership positions
- Take advantage of push factors, e.g. EU legislations
- Implement policy actions to raise awareness at both the bottom and the top of gendered organizational practices in recruitment, retention, and career progression
- Collect data about gender inequalities through existing databases, and surveys; analyse the needs (for the organisation and individuals); and design measures that are addressing the problems you have
- Provide training for all personnel, including leaders, get them on board to co-create training and have them lead by example. Don't forget to train members of selection committees!

6.4 Strengthening the gender dimension in research and teaching

Introducing and strengthening the gender dimension in research and teaching requires us to increase gender awareness in research content and funding; in team composition and leadership; in research funding procedures; gender our scientific publications; and increase gender sensitivity in teaching for a long-term effect.

Gender dimensions in teaching

Gendering teaching requires action before, during, and after a course.

Before: Review course materials for diverse gender perspectives, move beyond male-centric content, and invest in gender-inclusive communication training. Consider how gender affects learning processes and problem-solving to make sure everyone can be heard, address biases, identify inequalities in your subject, and refresh your knowledge of inclusive statistical methods. **During:** Stay up-to-date with research, highlight gender disparities, and encourage exploration of diverse perspectives. Acknowledge contributions from all genders, promote classroom diversity, and use inclusive language. Distinguish between sex (biological) and gender (socio-cultural). Use diverse, stereotype-free images, especially in professional or role-based contexts. **After:** Evaluate your efforts to confirm gender sensitivity by asking specific questions about how well it acknowledges gender considerations, if the teacher effectively addresses gender-related issues and present different gender-perspectives, if different opinions are welcome and discussed, and if gender-neutral language use is encouraged.

Advocating for formalisation: Promote formal policies and structures that embed gender, diversity and inclusion into research and learning environments, this shifts responsibility from individuals to institutions, ensuring sustainability and accountability. This includes **updating syllabi** to reflect gender-sensitive content, teaching students how to analyse from a gender perspective, critically assess texts and data, use non-androcentric frameworks and statistics, identify and address gender inequalities, especially in labour division in their own field, and evaluate policies through a gender lens. Formalisation also includes offering **regular, role-specific training for staff**, teaching them how to recognise and overcome biases, overcoming classroom conflicts, understanding how gender constructs affect individuals and science, and using real-life student experience to ensure representation.

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Table 13. What to do before:

- Include a gender perspective in your course
- Define gender-sensitive competences to be developed during teaching
- Critically evaluate course materials to ensure they encompass diverse gender perspectives and experiences
- Expand toolkit with alternative analytical frameworks that go beyond traditional white, able-bodied, middle-class male-centric viewpoints, enabling to offer more inclusive and nuanced perspectives within your field
- Invest in training to refine communication strategies, to promote inclusive dialogue and understanding among both peers and students
- Incorporate instructional methods that deepen awareness of how gender influences learning processes and problem-solving approaches, creating a supportive learning environment that caters to the needs of all students
- Address biases in course content by engaging in critical reflection to identify and address biases within your academic discipline, fostering awareness of how gender biases may manifest in research, teaching materials, and societal norms.
- Identify gender inequalities within your subject(s), demonstrating a commitment to promoting gender equity and social justice within your academic pursuits
- Training how to use statistical methods that account for diverse gender experiences, ensuring your research and analysis accurately reflect the complexities of gender dynamics in various contexts

Table 14. What to do during

- Continue to stay up to date with how gender is studied in your field and recent findings
- Highlight gender disparities and discuss the impact of the phenomenon on people, broken down by gender. For instance, in a sociology class studying poverty, examine how it affects women and men differently and keep in mind that gender is not only binary and keep in mind that gender is not only binary
- Encourage students to explore diverse perspectives and methodologies including and recognizing works by authors from different cultural backgrounds and genders
- Encourage diversity in your classroom by considering culture, age, and gender when forming student groups, to ensure a rich and inclusive learning environment
- Differentiate correctly between gender and sex and between gender identity and sex assigned at birth. Ensure your language reflects this difference.
- Make sure the images you use depict diversity and do not reinforce gender stereotypes. For example, show different gender persons in leadership positions or in care roles
- Mind your language and use inclusive terms and choose empowering terminology
- Training how to use statistical methods that account for diverse gender experiences, ensuring your research and analysis accurately reflect the complexities of gender dynamics in various contexts

Gender dimensions in research

While no single person or team can fix systemic gender inequality, collective efforts can drive meaningful change.

Brainstorming: Consider gender dynamics from the outset, including during brainstorming. Examine how stereotypes about binary sex and gender may influence research questions, methods, and literature review. **Proposal writing:** When crafting proposals, explicitly state the availability of gender-related evidence, formulate gender-sensitive hypotheses, and avoid generalizations. Consider social, historical, and cultural contexts, and ensure inclusive methodologies. **Team building & working:** Build diverse, multidisciplinary teams and ensure inclusive sampling by stratifying by sex, age, and socioeconomic status. Design variables and methods that reflect gender as a spectrum and account

for intersecting factors like ethnicity and orientation. Use culturally sensitive tools and disaggregate data by relevant axes. **Sharing & disseminating:** Present findings with gender sensitivity, using inclusive, non-discriminatory language. Avoid male-centric terms, use people-first language, and distinguish between sex and gender. Disseminate findings through gender-focused platforms to amplify diverse perspectives and promote equity in academia and beyond.

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